

SUSTAINABLE HIGHER EDUCATION UNDER THE FREE TUITION POLICY: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIC RESPONSES OF SUCS AND PRIVATE HEIS IN ZAMBOANGA DEL NORTE

Alex F. Tangapa II, PhD

ORCID NO: 0009-0006-0688-4603

College of Teacher Education, Jose Rizal Memorial State University – Katipunan Campus, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The implementation of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act (Republic Act No. 10931) has significantly transformed the higher education landscape in the Philippines by expanding access to tertiary education while simultaneously creating sustainability challenges for both State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This study examined the sustainability challenges and institutional responses of SUCs and private HEIs in Zamboanga del Norte during the Academic Year 2023–2024. Specifically, it determined the level of challenges encountered, identified institutional responses, assessed the effectiveness of these responses, and examined significant differences between SUCs and private HEIs in relation to the implementation of the UAQTE Act. The study employed a descriptive-quantitative research design with an exploratory component and involved thirty-nine (39) administrators and heads of offices from selected SUCs and private HEIs. Data were gathered using a validated self-constructed questionnaire and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, weighted mean, and independent samples t-test. The findings revealed that both SUCs and private HEIs experienced considerable challenges arising from the implementation of the UAQTE Act. The State University reported a high level of challenges, particularly in ensuring equitable access to students from lower socio-economic backgrounds, while private HEIs faced substantial challenges related to enrollment decline and financial sustainability. Both sectors implemented various strategies, including scholarship programs, enrollment management measures, institutional partnerships, retention policies, and resource optimization initiatives, to

address these challenges. The results further indicated that the State University demonstrated a higher level of effectiveness in responding to these challenges compared to private HEIs. However, no significant differences were found between the State University and private HEIs regarding the challenges encountered and the effectiveness of their responses. The study concludes that while the UAQTE Act has successfully increased access to higher education, it has also generated sustainability concerns that require strategic planning, sustainable financing, institutional resilience, and collaborative efforts among stakeholders to ensure the continued viability and quality of higher education institutions in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act, UAQTE Act, higher education institutions, sustainability challenges, institutional responses, State Universities and Colleges, private higher education institutions, educational policy, Philippines.*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, education is widely recognized as a fundamental driver of national development, social mobility, and economic growth. With a population exceeding 110 million, the country continues to invest in educational reforms aimed at enhancing human capital and improving the quality of life of its citizens. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2024) emphasized that education remains one of the most critical pillars of sustainable development, as it equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to participate productively in society and contribute to national progress. Similarly, the World Bank (2023) asserted that higher education plays a vital role in fostering innovation, workforce competitiveness, and economic resilience, particularly in developing countries pursuing inclusive growth and sustainable development.

Higher education, in particular, has long been regarded as a pathway to improved employment opportunities, higher earnings, and enhanced social well-being. Individuals with college degrees generally experience better labor market outcomes, increased productivity, and greater access to professional careers than those with lower educational attainment. Dickens et al. (2023) emphasized that higher education promotes meaningful civic participation, social engagement, and community development, thereby contributing not only to individual advancement but also to collective societal welfare. Likewise, Daway-Ducanes et al. (2022) found that higher educational attainment is positively associated with increased income levels, greater employment stability, and improved economic prospects, all of which are essential components of long-term national development. Supporting these findings, Hanushek and Woessmann (2015) argued that investments in education significantly influence economic productivity and national competitiveness by developing a skilled and adaptable workforce capable of responding to evolving global demands. Furthermore, Oketch (2021) noted that higher education contributes substantially to poverty reduction and social equity by providing individuals

from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds with opportunities for upward mobility and improved life outcomes.

Recent studies have also highlighted the expanding role of higher education in achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 4, which seeks to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. According to UNESCO (2023), access to quality tertiary education strengthens human capital formation, supports innovation, and enhances social cohesion, making it a critical factor in national and regional development. In the Philippine context, the increasing demand for higher education reflects society's recognition of education as a valuable investment capable of improving individual livelihoods while contributing to broader economic and social transformation.

Many prospective students, particularly those from impoverished backgrounds, face financial barriers to higher education, despite its importance. Affordability and socioeconomic factors are significant hurdles, as noted by Rana (2024), complicating equitable access to education for marginalized groups. In response, President Duterte led the Philippine government to pass the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act (UAQTE) in 2017. The law aims to make it easier for people to get an education by offering free tuition and other fees at state universities and colleges, as well as other support programs. This reform has led to a notable increase in student enrollment across state institutions, particularly in Zamboanga del Norte, as students transition from private colleges seeking free education.

However, the influx poses sustainability challenges for State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), including strains on facilities, classroom overcrowding, and faculty shortages, which raise concerns about maintaining educational quality amid limited funding. Meanwhile, private higher education institutions face distinct threats to their viability, as the shift towards SUCs jeopardizes their operational sustainability and capacity for improvements. Addressing these emerging sustainability challenges necessitates comprehensive investigation to inform strategic planning within higher education, ensuring both the resilience of individual institutions and the broader educational ecosystem in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the sustainability challenges and institutional responses of State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the implementation of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act in the Philippines.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of challenges faced by the SUC and private HEIs as results of the implementation of Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act?

2. What are the SUC and private HEIs' responses to the above challenges?
3. How effective are there responses of the SUC and private HEIs towards the challenges faced?
4. Is there a significant difference on the challenges and the responses of the SUC and private HEIs in the implementation of UAQTE Act?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-quantitative research design with an exploratory component to investigate the sustainability challenges encountered by State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) arising from the implementation of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act (Republic Act No. 10931). The descriptive aspect of the study provided a systematic and objective assessment of the extent to which higher education institutions experienced various challenges associated with the policy's implementation. Meanwhile, the exploratory component enabled a more comprehensive examination of emerging issues and institutional realities, allowing the researcher to gain more profound insights into the adaptive strategies and responses adopted by HEIs. Through the use of a structured survey instrument, the study generated quantitative data that facilitated the measurement of challenges and response effectiveness. Furthermore, inferential statistical techniques were utilized to determine whether significant differences existed between SUCs and private HEIs regarding the challenges they encountered and the effectiveness of their corresponding responses. This methodological approach was deemed appropriate, as it provided both a broad and in-depth understanding of the implications of the UAQTE Act on institutional sustainability.

The study was conducted among Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Province of Zamboanga del Norte during the academic year 2023–2024. As one of the key provinces in the Zamboanga Peninsula, Zamboanga del Norte hosts a diverse higher education sector composed of both public and private institutions that play a vital role in developing skilled human resources and supporting regional socio-economic growth. The implementation of the UAQTE Act has significantly transformed the higher education landscape by expanding access to tertiary education, influencing enrollment patterns, altering financial structures, and affecting institutional competitiveness. These changes have generated both opportunities and challenges for higher education institutions. By focusing on HEIs within Zamboanga del Norte, the study sought to provide empirical evidence on how institutions navigate policy-induced changes while maintaining operational sustainability, educational quality, and organizational resilience. We expect the findings to enhance policy and strategic planning within the higher education sector.

The respondents of the study consisted of administrators and heads of offices from selected State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Zamboanga del Norte. These individuals were chosen because of their direct involvement in institutional planning, policy implementation, resource management, and decision-making processes, making them highly knowledgeable regarding the effects of

the UAQTE Act on their respective institutions. A total of thirty-nine (39) respondents participated in the study, of whom fourteen (14) represented the state university system and twenty-five (25) represented private HEIs. The difference in the number of respondents reflects the educational landscape of the province, where only one state university system operates through multiple campuses, while several independently managed private institutions are present. A purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure that participants possessed the necessary expertise, experience, and administrative responsibilities relevant to the objectives of the study. This sampling approach enhanced the reliability and relevance of the information gathered regarding institutional challenges and responses.

Data were collected using a validated self-constructed questionnaire developed from the provisions of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act (Republic Act No. 10931), its Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR), related government issuances, and pertinent literature and studies. The instrument was designed to capture comprehensive information relevant to the study objectives and consisted of three major sections. The first section gathered demographic and institutional profile information. The second section measured the level of sustainability challenges experienced by SUCs and private HEIs as a result of the implementation of the UAQTE Act. The third section assessed the effectiveness of institutional responses and strategies employed to address these challenges. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale to ensure consistency, comparability, and ease of interpretation. Prior to its administration, the questionnaire underwent content validation by experts in educational management, policy studies, and research methodology to establish its validity, clarity, relevance, and appropriateness. Necessary revisions were incorporated based on the validators' recommendations to enhance the instrument's overall quality and reliability.

To facilitate data collection, the researcher first secured an endorsement from the dean and obtained formal approval from the administrators of the participating higher education institutions in Zamboanga del Norte. Upon receiving authorization, the researcher personally distributed copies of the validated questionnaire to the identified respondents. The objectives, significance, and procedures of the study were clearly explained to ensure informed participation. Respondents were likewise assured that all information collected would be treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic and research purposes. After allowing sufficient time for completion, the accomplished questionnaires were retrieved, reviewed for completeness and consistency, and organized for data processing. The collected data were subsequently encoded, tabulated, and prepared for statistical analysis. The results were then interpreted and discussed in relation to the study objectives and existing literature to provide meaningful conclusions and recommendations.

The gathered data were analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Frequency counts and percentages were employed to describe the profile of the respondents and summarize institutional characteristics and responses related to the implementation of the UAQTE Act. The weighted mean was utilized to determine the level of sustainability challenges experienced by SUCs and private HEIs

and to assess the effectiveness of their responses in addressing these challenges. To examine whether significant differences existed between state universities and colleges and private higher education institutions regarding the challenges encountered and the effectiveness of their responses, the independent samples t-test was employed. All statistical analyses were conducted using a significance level of 0.05, providing a basis for accepting or rejecting the null hypotheses. These statistical tools enabled the researcher to derive objective, reliable, and meaningful interpretations of the data, thereby supporting evidence-based conclusions regarding the impact of the UAQTE Act on the sustainability of higher education institutions.

RESULTS

Level of Challenges faced by the State University and Private HEIs as results of the Implementation of Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act

The implementation of the UAQTE Act has presented significant challenges for both state universities and private higher education institutions (HEIs). The State University categorized the challenges into four groups, with the greatest difficulty being the provision of equitable access to free higher education for those from lower socio-economic backgrounds, rated at 3.96. Overall, the university perceived the implementation of the UAQTE Act as highly challenging, scoring 3.55. This indicates that changes in how students access tertiary education and increased attendance are creating new demands and challenges. Conversely, private HEIs faced high levels of challenges across nearly all categories, except for Latent and External Challenges, which were rated as average at 3.37. This signifies those private institutions, which depend on tuition-paying students, are severely affected by the desire for free higher education, resulting in numerous difficulties stemming from the UAQTE Act's implementation.

State University and private HEIs' response to the above challenges

The responses from State Universities (SUC) and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) regarding the implementation challenges of the UAQTE Act. The table shows that some beneficial practices in private HEIs, such as prioritizing disadvantaged but academically capable students, were not utilized by the state university. Private HEIs provided significant support for access to quality education, including outreach to remote areas and online programs. Conversely, while the SUC accepted students regardless of socio-economic status, they faced challenges due to increased enrollment and inadequately providing necessary resources and facilities.

Additionally, the report discusses how private HEIs have responded to financial challenges. To compete with SUC, private HEIs have used government-funded scholarships and charged fees. The SUC, however, reported budget constraints and prioritized expenses, searching for additional funding from CHED. It addresses responses to policy and mechanism challenges. Private HEIs focused on career guidance and scholarships while maintaining quality through strict admission policies. The SUC

similarly emphasized retention policies and collaborations to uphold educational standards. Finally, it reveals responses to latent and external challenges. Both SUC and private HEIs are committed to inclusivity in higher education, implementing admission and retention policies, and creating additional facilities to accommodate rising student populations while ensuring quality education. Thus, HEIs must remain responsive to the evolving educational landscape and societal demands to maintain competitiveness and quality.

Level of Responses of the State University and Private HEIs as results of the Implementation of Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act

The level of effectiveness of responses indicates that the State University managed the challenges posed by the UAQTE Act more effectively (3.85) than private higher education institutions (3.39). This suggests that the State University, which relies more on government subsidies, has greater resources and options for responding to these challenges compared to private HEIs, which depend on revenue from tuition fees.

Significant Difference in the Level of Challenges and Responses faced by the State University and Private HEIs as results of the Implementation of Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act

The analysis reveals that there are no significant differences in the challenges and responses experienced by the State University and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) as indicated by a t-value of -0.216 and a p-value of 0.830 for challenges, and a t-value of 1.307 and p-value of 0.199 for responses. Both institutions faced similar challenges under the implementation of the UAQTE Act and demonstrated comparable effectiveness in addressing these challenges, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

DISCUSSION

The implementation of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act (UAQTE) has introduced substantial challenges for both state universities and private higher education institutions (HEIs). The State University reported that the most pressing difficulty is ensuring equitable access for students from lower socio-economic backgrounds ($M = 3.96$), reflecting national concerns that free tuition increases demand but strains institutional resources such as faculty, facilities, and student support systems (Daway-Ducanes et al., 2022). The overall challenge rating of 3.55 suggests that the policy's rapid rise in enrollments is changing how students access services and putting pressure on SUCs to keep quality high as they grow (Corpuz et al., 2022). Conversely, private HEIs experienced high levels of difficulty in nearly all areas, with only Latent and External Challenges rated moderately at 3.37. This aligns with recent findings that private institutions heavily reliant on tuition revenues which face enrollment declines and financial instability as more students migrate to state universities to avail of free education (Rana, 2024). Thus, while UAQTE promotes broader access, it simultaneously produces uneven

impacts across the higher education sector, requiring strategic responses to sustain both public and private institutions.

Both State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines have reacted differently to the challenges posed by the UAQTE Act, reflecting structural differences. Private HEIs have prioritized academically strong yet disadvantaged students, expanded outreach, and offered flexible online programs, which support their competitiveness amid limited enrollment (Rana, 2024). In contrast, SUCs have grappled with resource constraints due to rapid enrollment growth from free higher education initiatives, leading to concerns about facility and program quality (Daway-Ducanes et al., 2022). Financial pressures pushed private HEIs to maximize government scholarships and maintain fee-based services, leveraging diversified funding to adapt to policy changes (Lee et al., 2022), while SUCs struggled with budget issues reliant on CHED support (Corpuz et al., 2022). Both sectors emphasized the importance of retention policies, scholarships, and collaboration to ensure educational quality in the face of rising enrollment (Almerez & Duping, 2022). Ultimately, both SUCs and private HEIs are adapting their admissions practices and expanding facilities to meet evolving educational needs, highlighting the necessity for institutional resilience and strategic planning under the UAQTE framework (Mirador & Lluz, 2021).

Further, the State University responded more effectively to the challenges of the UAQTE Act than private HEIs. This higher effectiveness is likely due to SUCs' access to government funding, which enables them to adjust more readily to increased enrollment and resource demands (Almerez & Duping, 2022). In contrast, private HEIs, which rely heavily on tuition revenue, face greater financial strain and fewer options for enhancing services or facilities, reducing their ability to respond effectively (Lee et al., 2020; Rana, 2024). These results highlight how public institutions are structurally better positioned to manage policy-driven changes than their private counterparts.

Finally, the results indicate no significant differences between the State University and private HEIs in the challenges they encountered and the responses they implemented under the UAQTE Act, as shown by non-significant p-values for both challenges ($p = .830$) and responses ($p = .199$). This suggests that despite structural differences—such as funding sources and enrollment patterns—both public and private institutions experienced comparable pressures related to increased student demand, resource limitations, and policy adjustments. Recent studies likewise note that the implementation of free higher education has created sector-wide challenges that affect all HEIs, regardless of type, including institutional capacity strains and the need for academic resilience (Almerez & Duping, 2022; Mirador & Lluz, 2021). The absence of statistically significant differences therefore supports the conclusion that both institutions confronted similar conditions and responded with relatively equal effectiveness, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Conclusions

The implementation of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act has generated significant sustainability challenges for both State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Zamboanga del Norte. While the policy has successfully expanded access to higher education, it has simultaneously created institutional pressures related to enrollment growth, resource allocation, financial sustainability, infrastructure capacity, and the maintenance of educational quality. These challenges have affected both sectors, although they manifest differently according to institutional structures and funding mechanisms.

State Universities and Colleges and private HEIs have adopted various strategies to address the challenges brought about by the implementation of the UAQTE Act. SUCs have focused on maximizing government support, implementing retention policies, prioritizing resource allocation, and establishing partnerships to sustain educational quality despite increased enrollment. Meanwhile, private HEIs have strengthened scholarship programs, expanded outreach initiatives, enhanced flexible learning opportunities, and adopted competitive strategies to attract and retain students. These responses demonstrate the commitment of higher education institutions to remain resilient and responsive amid changing educational policies.

The findings further reveal that the responses implemented by both sectors were generally effective in addressing the challenges posed by the UAQTE Act. However, State Universities and Colleges demonstrated a higher level of effectiveness than private HEIs, primarily due to their access to government subsidies and institutional support mechanisms. Such advantages enabled SUCs to better manage increased student demand and operational pressures associated with the implementation of free higher education.

Moreover, the study established that there were no significant differences between the State University and private HEIs regarding the challenges encountered and the effectiveness of their responses to the implementation of the UAQTE Act. This indicates that, despite differences in governance structures, funding sources, and operational frameworks, both sectors experienced comparable sustainability concerns and employed similar adaptive measures. The implementation of the UAQTE Act has therefore created sector-wide challenges that require collective and coordinated responses from policymakers, educational leaders, and stakeholders.

Overall, the study concludes that while the UAQTE Act has significantly improved access to tertiary education, its long-term success depends on the capacity of both public and private higher education institutions to sustain quality educational services amid evolving demands. Strengthened institutional support, strategic planning, sustainable financing mechanisms, and collaborative partnerships are essential to ensuring the resilience, competitiveness, and sustainability of the higher education sector in the Philippines.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommended that State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) strengthen their institutional planning, resource allocation, and capacity-building initiatives to effectively address the increasing enrollment and operational demands resulting from the implementation of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education (UAQTE) Act. Investments in faculty development, infrastructure expansion, learning resources, and student support services should be prioritized to ensure that the quality of education is maintained despite the growing number of beneficiaries of free tertiary education.

Private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are encouraged to develop innovative and sustainable strategies to remain competitive within the evolving higher education landscape. These strategies may include expanding scholarship and financial assistance programs, strengthening industry and community partnerships, enhancing flexible learning modalities, and offering specialized academic programs that address emerging labor market needs. Such initiatives may help improve enrollment, strengthen institutional sustainability, and ensure continued access to quality education for students who choose private institutions.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED), together with other concerned government agencies, should formulate and implement policies that provide balanced support to both public and private higher education institutions. While the UAQTE Act has significantly improved access to tertiary education, complementary interventions are necessary to address its unintended consequences on private HEIs and to ensure the overall stability and sustainability of the higher education sector. Financial assistance, institutional development grants, and capacity-enhancement programs may be considered to help institutions effectively respond to emerging challenges.

Policymakers should regularly review and evaluate the implementation of the UAQTE Act to determine its long-term impact on educational quality, institutional sustainability, and equitable access to higher education. Continuous policy assessment will enable government agencies and educational stakeholders to identify gaps, address emerging concerns, and develop evidence-based improvements that will strengthen the effectiveness of the program while safeguarding the interests of all higher education institutions.

Furthermore, higher education institutions should foster stronger collaboration and partnerships among themselves, government agencies, industries, and community organizations. Such collaborations can facilitate resource sharing, research initiatives, faculty development opportunities, and innovative academic programs that contribute to institutional resilience and long-term sustainability. Strengthened partnerships can also help institutions adapt more effectively to policy changes and evolving societal needs.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies in other regions of the Philippines using larger samples and additional variables related to

institutional performance, financial sustainability, student outcomes, and policy effectiveness. Qualitative and mixed-methods studies may also be undertaken to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences, perspectives, and adaptive strategies of administrators, faculty members, and students affected by the implementation of the UAQTE Act. Such studies would further enrich the body of knowledge and provide valuable insights for policy development and institutional improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in strict adherence to the fundamental ethical principles of research, namely respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, to ensure the protection, dignity, and welfare of all participants. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and no respondent was subjected to coercion, undue influence, or any form of pressure to participate. Prior to data collection, all participants were provided with a clear and comprehensive explanation of the study's objectives, significance, procedures, potential benefits, and their rights as research participants. Informed consent was obtained from each respondent, signifying their voluntary agreement to participate after fully understanding the nature and purpose of the research. Participants were likewise informed of their right to decline participation or withdraw from the study at any stage without any adverse consequences or penalties.

The researcher ensured the confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity of all respondents throughout the entire research process. No personally identifiable information was collected, recorded, or disclosed in any part of the study. To safeguard participants' identities, responses were assigned codes and treated with the highest level of confidentiality. All data gathered were used exclusively for academic and research purposes and were stored securely in password-protected files accessible only to the researchers. Appropriate measures were implemented to prevent unauthorized access, misuse, loss, or disclosure of research data.

The study was designed to minimize risks and avoid any form of physical, psychological, social, or professional harm to participants. The questionnaire contained no sensitive, intrusive, discriminatory, or potentially distressing questions. The researchers exercised honesty, objectivity, transparency, and professional integrity throughout all phases of the investigation, including data collection, analysis, interpretation, and reporting of findings. Every effort was made to ensure that the results accurately reflected the data collected and that no information was fabricated, manipulated, omitted, or misrepresented.

Furthermore, the study complied with institutional ethical standards and accepted principles of responsible research conduct. The use of artificial intelligence-assisted tools, such as QuillBot and similar language-enhancement applications, was limited exclusively to grammar checking, language refinement, sentence restructuring, and paraphrasing for improved readability. These tools were not utilized in generating research findings, interpreting results, analyzing data, formulating conclusions, or making

recommendations. All intellectual, analytical, and scholarly contributions remained solely the responsibility of the researcher.

Finally, the author further declares that there are no known competing financial interests, professional affiliations, personal relationships, or other circumstances that could have influenced, or appeared to influence, the conduct, analysis, interpretation, or reporting of this study. No conflicts of interest, whether financial, academic, institutional, or personal in nature, exist in relation to this research. The study was conducted independently and objectively, with the sole intention of contributing to the advancement of knowledge and evidence-based decision-making in the higher education sector. Ethical responsibility, academic integrity, and professional accountability were upheld at all times to ensure the credibility, trustworthiness, and scholarly value of the research.

Acknowledgments

The author wishes to express his profound gratitude to Jose Rizal Memorial State University (JRMSU) for its unwavering support, academic guidance, and commitment to fostering research and scholarly excellence. The University's dedication to advancing knowledge and promoting a culture of inquiry provided an enabling environment that significantly contributed to the successful completion of this study. The institutional resources, encouragement, and opportunities extended by JRMSU were invaluable throughout the research process.

The author likewise extends his heartfelt appreciation to his beloved wife for her steadfast love, patience, understanding, and unwavering support throughout the conduct of this research. Her constant encouragement, sacrifices, and belief in his capabilities served as a source of strength and inspiration during the challenges and demands of this study. Her emotional support and motivation played a vital role in the completion of this scholarly endeavor.

The author also expresses his sincere gratitude to all administrators, respondents, colleagues, mentors, and individuals who, in one way or another, contributed their time, expertise, assistance, and encouragement to this undertaking. Their cooperation and support greatly enriched the quality and successful completion of this research.

Above all, the author offers his deepest gratitude to Almighty God for His divine guidance, wisdom, strength, and countless blessings throughout the research journey. His grace, mercy, and providence made the successful completion of this study possible.

To all who contributed directly or indirectly to the realization of this work, the author conveys his sincere appreciation and heartfelt thanks.

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